

phoglucoase isomerase (PGI), isocitrate dehydrogenase (ICD), phosphogluconate dehydrogenase (PGD), and superoxide dismutase (SOD).

We compared zymograms of 63 extracts of an *Anabaena* strain (PCC 7120) for these 4 enzymes: 54 of them were obtained from liquid cultures on BG 11 medium without N. They were

1. grown in 3 environments:

- a) *laboratory*: $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, continuous lighting provided by cold white neon tubes, light intensity about 600 lux;
- b) *phytotron*: $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, continuous lighting provided by neon tubes and incandescent bulbs, light intensity about 5 klux;
- c) *greenhouse*: $25\text{-}38^\circ\text{C}$, maximum light intensity around 90 klux.

2. harvested 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 d after inoculation.

3. extracted after deep freezing using three methods: a) simple thawing, b) manual grinding using a glass rod, c) sonication for 5 min, with the culture in an ice bath.

The other 9 extracts were obtained from cultures on solid medium (BG 11 medium without N, 1% bacto agar) grown in the laboratory under continuous lighting (600 lux). Individual colonies were harvested at 10, 13, 15, 17, 20, 22, 24, 27, and 30 d after plating and extracted by manual grinding in cold distilled water.

We observed the following (Fig. 1):

- For a given extraction procedure, there was no difference between laboratory and phytotron grown samples whatever their age. In green-

2. Zymograms of PGI (a) and PGD (b) from various BGA strains.

house grown samples, the intensity of the bands decreased with the age of the material and a qualitative inconsistency was observed for ICD.

- Manual grinding increased the intensity of the bands as compared with a simple thawing of deep frozen samples. Sonication had a similar effect, but induced development of a new PGI band and the disappearance of an ICD band.
- In material produced on solid medium, a same single band was observed for each of the four enzymes, at all colony ages. This band was the only one common to all the zymograms of the samples grown in liquid medium.

Manual grinding of individual colonies grown on solid medium appears to

minimize possible artifacts by selecting bands that consistently appear with the other procedures of extraction and in material grown under different conditions. A major additional advantage is that petri dishes inoculated with suspension dilutions of soil for routine BGA counts can be used directly for isozyme characterization.

This method was tested with nine other *Anabaena* species and nine different genera. In all cases, a single major band was observed for each of the PGI, PGD, and SOD enzymes. Some strains, however, did not produce an ICD band. Variation among strains was large (Fig. 2), which indicates good potential for strain identification. □

Evapotranspiration and water use of rice in central India

A. S. R. A. S. Sastri, B. L. Chandrakar, and B. R. Chandrawanshi, Zonal Agricultural Research Station (ZARS), J. N. Agricultural University, Raipur 492012, India

We studied evapotranspiration and water use of Samridhi rice, a 125-d variety, from 1979 to 1983 at ZARS, Raipur ($21^\circ16' \text{N}$, $81^\circ36' \text{E}$). Rice was planted in $40 \times 40\text{-m}$ plots with 2 volumetric lysimeters in the center of each field.

Lysimetric evapotranspiration (E_T), open-pan evaporation (E_O), grain yield, and water use efficiency of rice over 5 yr in Raipur, India.

Year	E_T (mm)	E_O (mm)	$E_T:E_O$	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency (kg/ha per mm of E_T)
1979	570	418	1.36	2.6	4.6
1980	705	396	1.78	3.8	5.4
1981	788	458	1.72	3.6	4.6
1982	695	428	1.62	3.2	4.7
1983	473	382	1.24	3.9	8.3
Av	645	416	1.55	3.4	5.3

Soil was a sandy loam. Twenty-five- to 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted

about 20 Jul. NPK was applied at 80-40-40 kg/ha.

From transplanting to harvest (about 100 d) lysimetric evapotranspiration (E_T) averaged 645 mm versus 416 mm open pan evaporation (E_O) (see table). Rerage $E_T:E_O$ (crop coefficient K) was 1.55, varying from 1.78 in 1980 to 1.24 in 1983. Average grain yield was 3.4 t/ha. Water use efficiency (kg/ha per mm of E_T) averaged 5.3.

To better understand water use during the growing season, the $E_T:E_O$ values for each week were calculated for 5 yr and averaged (see figure). During peak vegetative growth, rice at Raipur required 1.7 times E_O for % losses. $E_T:E_O$ decreases rapidly at maturity. □

Water use pattern of rice (var. R-2384) crop over 5 yr in Raipur, India.

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Intercropping rice and cotton

V. K. Khaddar and N. Ray, Project for Management of Salt-Affected Soil, College of Agriculture, Indore, Madhya Pradesh 452001, India

To reduce the risk of farming under erratic monsoon conditions, we evaluated rice + cotton intercropping in black-cotton soil at the Agriculture College Farm at Indore (see figure). Cotton was planted on ridges and rice in furrows to suit the moisture needs of each.

Ridges were 15 cm high and 40 cm across at the base. Seeds of Barwaha cotton, which tolerates standing water, were sown 3 Jul 1983 and drought-resistant, salt-tolerant CSR-4 rice was transplanted 27 Jul 1983. At transplanting, there was no standing water and furrows were not puddled, but the soil was soft from a recent rain. Rice was transplanted at 30-cm spacing to allow more light to reach the crop. Within 80 cm, there were 2 rows of rice and 1 row of cotton (see figure). Furrow irrigation was applied as needed.

Rice was harvested the 1st week of Nov when cotton had begun to shed leaves, which facilitates sowing a rabi

Rice + cotton intercropping.

crop such as barley in the furrows. Rice + cotton intercropping gave per hectare yields of 1.5 t cotton, 2.5 t rice grain,

and 3.9 t rice straw. We are conducting further studies to identify optimum plant spacings for both crops. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.